

**ATTITUDE OF SCHEDULED CASTE PARENTS TOWARDS GIRLS'
EDUCATION IN RELATION TO THEIR SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS
IN UTTAR DINAJPUR**

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Abstract:

Education is one of the major instruments of social change and it is the force, which brings changes in the traditional outlook of the people, and it develops insight for judging things in their context. It is assumed that more the percentage of educated people more will be the rate of development. The Latin word "Educare" which is the root of the English word "education," implies to nourish or cause to thrive (Patel, 1991). Education is essential for all members of society. The survival of nations lies in education. The objectives of the study are to examine the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents towards education of their girl child in relation to socio-economic status. Descriptive method is selected for study. The findings of the study are that

there is significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education in relation to Socio-Economic Status variation, there is significant difference between the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents having high socio-economic status and having low socio-economic status towards girls' education in rural areas and there is significant difference between the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents having high socio-economic status and having low socio-economic status towards girls' education in urban areas.

Key Words: Attitude, Girls' Education, Scheduled caste parents, Locale

1.0. Introduction

Education is very important for every child whether it is a boy or a girl. It is said that some communities still discriminate against the education of the girl child. Women and girls in the developing country are often denied opportunities for education. Lack of education limits prospects, decrease family income, reduce health, put women and girls at risk of trafficking and exploitation and limit the economic advancement of the entire country. About two centuries back, education was merely informative. The child was considered as a pitcher into which the teacher poured "gallon of empirical facts/" The child was made to remain quiet and receptive.

But today the world is passing through rapid changes. For a country which has accepted the goal of democratic egalitarian society, promotion and development of women's education is foregone commitment. Indeed, in the overall development of a country, women's education is greatly needed and it is also the key to unlock the door to modernization. World education believes that education for girls and women is the single most effective way to improve the lives of individual families as well as to bring economic development to poor communities worldwide.

The girl child of today is tomorrow's woman. If tomorrow's woman is to become equal partner with man, there is a great need to accord the girl child her rightful share of dignity and opportunity. The system of patriarchy, tradition and culture have greatly hindered the maximum exploration of girl's strength and intelligence in the educational process. Women are

often perceived as a utility asset to undertake all household chores in a traditional society and the ideal roles assigned to them are those of daughter, sister, wives and mothers. In such a society, it is a common belief that women are inferior to men. Opinions and advises of women are not entertained by men in all forms of decision making.

Girl's education has a positive impact on their outlook which helps them to improve their status. Education spread their outlook in different sectors and their outlook broadened. They become thriftily independent and thus elevate their standard of living.

Home is the first school and mother is the first teacher. And therefore, a society cannot function effectively when the women are uneducated and ignorant. Thus, women's education is very important and essential for the development of the society or the nation. A common view that spending money on girls is useless or that it's an extravagant thing to educate them as they will be married off to another family hinders their education. Though other areas are important, girls getting education through schools is the single most effective way of tackling poverty. It increases life expectancy, reduces family size, improved child survival, raises productivity and enable women to demand a voice in both private and public life. "Education of boys is education of one person, but education of a girl is the education of the entire family," said Jawaharlal Nehru, while underlying the importance of girls' education. Therefore, in order to bring upliftment of the society and development education of girls is the priority step to be taken up.

Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru once said, "To awaken the people, it is the women who must be awakened; once she is on the move, the family moves, the nation moves". Society cannot progress with educated men and uneducated women. No society can develop materially and morally where the bulk of its female members remain illiterate and devoid of education.

1.2. Reviews of related literature

Huisman, Rani, and Smits, (2010) studied the role of socio-economic and cultural factors, and of characteristics of the educational infrastructure on primary school enrolment, The sample constituted 70,000 children living in 439 districts of 26 states of India. The results indicated that

most of the variation in educational enrolment (around 70%) is explained by factors at the household level, of which socio-economic factors are most important. And the result also indicated that, in the cities schooling decisions are hardly influenced by supply-side factors. In rural areas, however, these factors do play an important role. If there are fewer schools or teachers, or if the local culture is more patriarchal, rural children (in particular girls) participate substantially less. The major finding of this respect was that in rural areas inequalities between socio-economic status groups are lower if more schools and teachers are available.

It has been found that three major determinants of educational enrolment: socio-economic status, educational infrastructure, and culture have an impact on primary school participation in India (Evangelista de Carvalho Filho, (2008); Mingat, (2007); Shavit and Blossfeld, (1993); Jencks, (1972); Coleman et al., (1966). Socio-economic indices like the characteristics of households, parental income, wealth, education and occupation, have long been known to be major determinants of educational enrolment and achievement in both developing and developed countries.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

The objectives are as under:

1. To examine the difference between the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents having high socio-economic status and having low socio-economic status towards girls' education.
2. To examine the difference between the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents having high socio-economic status and having low socio-economic status towards girls' education in rural areas.
3. To examine the difference between the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents having high socio-economic status and having low socio-economic status towards girls' education in urban areas.

1.4. Hypothesis of the study

On the basis of the above objectives, the following hypotheses will be formulated:

H₁: There is no significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education in relation to Socio-Economic Status variation.

H₂: There is no significant difference between the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents having high socio-economic status and having low socio-economic status towards girls' education in rural areas.

H₃: There is no significant difference between the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents having high socio-economic status and having low socio-economic status towards girls' education in urban areas.

1.5. Operational definitions of the terms used

Attitude: An organism state of readiness to respond in a characteristic way to a stimulus (Merriam Webster). The way a person views something or tends to behave towards it, often in an evolution way.

Education: The modification of the attitude and behaviour through training in formal learning systems.

1.6. Scope of the Study

Girls are viewed as the most deprived and disadvantaged section of the Indian society. Indian girls and girls have been subjected to various kinds of social discrimination including education. We know that Scheduled caste girls are still lagging behind in the entire sphere and are deprived of all the educational opportunities especially in the state West Bengal. It is a matter of concern for me to analyze the impact of 'Girls' education' on empowerment of Scheduled caste girls in West Bengal with special reference to Uttar Dinajpur district.

2.0. Method of the study

For the present study, the descriptive method of research has been used.

2.1. Research Design

It is a descriptive study which investigates the attitude of Scheduled caste parents towards their girl child education. Block 1 consists of 200 samples and Block 2 consists of 200 samples.

2.2. Population

The study aimed at studying the attitude of Scheduled caste parents towards their girl child education in both rural and urban area of Uttar Dinajpur District of West Bengal.

2.3. Sample

Sample were taken from 2 Blocks of UTTAR DINAJPUR district of West Bengal according to their administrative block. A sample of 400 house hold (Parents) were selected by purposive method. The variables of the study is Socio-Economic Status (High SES & Low SES).

2.4. Sampling technique

For the present study the researcher used Purposive Sampling Technique for data collection.

2.5. Tools used for data collection:

The tools used for this study were:

Socio-Economic Status scale of Mishra (2014) had been used to determine the socio-economic background of parents of the girls' children. The scale constituted of three parts education, occupation and income. Each of these categories had 9 sub-categories. The total score of sub-categories checked in each criterion show the socio-economic status of the subject. The description of the socio-economic status scale was given item wise along with weightage in parenthesis had been appended to this report as Appendix B. The scale was standardized over the population of Odisha, secondary schools of Cuttack, Puri and Bhubaneswar. The validity and

reliability of the scale was determined where the retest reliability co-efficient was found to be 0.87, concurrent validity co-efficient is 0.61 and inter-rater reliability index was 0.93.

2.6. Techniques of data collection:

The following techniques have been used for this study:

- Questioning techniques were adopted for collection of data through questionnaires.
- The test of significance of difference ('t') between the means of two contrasting sub-samples was calculated to find out significant difference in two sub samples in relation to socio-economic status.

3.0. Results and Discussion

The result has been organized under differential analysis and study of relationship on the variables and between the variables. For determining the significance of differences between the mean of the contrast "t" test was adopted and the value of "t" ratio is presented in the table followed by discussion. The result obtained in the present study was studied in corroboration with other studies.

3.1. Socio-Economic Status variation differences on scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education

One of the objectives of the study was to be found out if there exist any Socio-Economic Status variation differences on scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education, therefore the null hypothesis was stated as "there is no significant difference in scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education in relation to Socio-Economic Status variation".

In order to find out differences if any of the scores on scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education of High Socio-Economic Status and Low Socio-Economic Status, the test of significance of difference between the means of two sub samples was calculated and

tested for significance. The result has been presented in the following table:

Table 1: Summary of test of significance of differences between the Socio-Economic Status variation of scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education

Socio-Economic Status variation	N	Mean	S. D	SE _D	't'	Remark
High Socio-Economic Status	200	58.17	22.67	0.55	3.83	Significant
Low Socio-Economic Status	200	76.18	27.23			

Critical value of 't' with df (98) at 0.01=2.63 and 0.05=1.98

The obtained value 3.83 is greater than the tabular value at 0.05 levels 1.98 and at 0.01 level 2.63 so it is significant and the null hypothesis that states there exist no significant difference between the Socio-Economic Status variation of scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education will be rejected. This finding was in conformity with the findings of Breen & Goldthorpe,1997, Huisman, Rani, and Smits, 2010, Bhalotra & Heady, 2003; Basu, Das and Dutta, 2003, Evangelista de Carvalho Filho, 2008; Mingat, 2007; Shavit and Blossfeld, 1993; Jencks, 1972; Coleman et al., 1966 and Bauch 1991.

3.2. Socio-Economic Status variation differences on Rural scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education

One of the objectives of the study was to be found out if there exist any Socio-Economic Status variation differences on rural scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education, therefore the null hypothesis was stated as "there is no significant difference in rural scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education in relation to Socio-Economic Status variation". In order to find out differences if any of the scores on rural scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education of High Socio-Economic Status and Low Socio-Economic Status, the

test of significance of difference between the means of two sub samples was calculated and tested for significance. The result has been presented in the following table:

Table 2: Summary of test of significance of differences between the Socio-Economic Status variation of Rural scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education

Rural Socio-Economic Status variation	N	Mean	S. D	SE _D	't'	Remark
Rural High Socio-Economic Status	100	59	21.05	0.54	3.81	Significant
Rural Low Socio-Economic Status	100	66	26.12			

Critical value of 't' with df (98) at 0.01=2.63 and 0.05=1.98

The obtained value 3.81 is greater than the tabular value at 0.05 levels 1.98 and at 0.01 level 2.63 so it is significant and the null hypothesis that states there exist no significant difference between the Socio-Economic Status variation of rural scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education will be rejected. This finding was in conformity with the findings of Breen & Goldthorpe,1997, Huisman, Rani, and Smits, 2010, Bhalotra & Heady, 2003; Basu, Das and Dutta, 2003, Evangelista de Carvalho Filho, 2008; Mingat, 2007; Shavit and Blossfeld, 1993; Jencks, 1972; Coleman et al., 1966 and Bauch 1991.

3.3. Socio-Economic Status variation differences on Urban scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education

One of the objectives of the study was to be found out if there exist any Socio-Economic Status variation differences on urban scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education, therefore the null hypothesis was stated as "there is no significant difference in urban scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' Education in relation to Socio-Economic Status

variation”.

In order to find out differences if any of the scores on urban scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education of High Socio-Economic Status and Low Socio-Economic Status, the test of significance of difference between the means of two sub samples was calculated and tested for significance. The result has been presented in the following table:

Table 3: Summary of test of significance of differences between the Socio-Economic Status variation of Urban scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education

Urban Socio-Economic Status variation	N	Mean	S. D	SE _D	‘t’	Remark
Urban High Socio-Economic Status	100	51	22	0.85	3.65	Significant
Urban Low Socio-Economic Status	100	74	26			

Critical value of ‘t’ with df (98) at 0.01=2.63 and 0.05=1.98

The obtained value 3.65 is greater than the tabular value at 0.05 levels 1.98 and at 0.01 level 2.63 so it is significant and the null hypothesis that states there exist no significant difference between the Socio-Economic Status variation of urban scheduled caste Parents’ attitude towards girls’ Education will be rejected. This finding was in conformity with the findings of Breen & Goldthorpe,1997, Huisman, Rani, and Smits, 2010, Bhalotra & Heady, 2003; Basu, Das and Dutta, 2003, Evangelista de Carvalho Filho, 2008; Mingat, 2007; Shavit and Blossfeld, 1993; Jencks, 1972; Coleman et al., 1966, Sen, 1992, Caldwell, 1982 and Bauch 1991.

4.0. Findings of the Study

After thorough study and data analysis, following findings had been noticed:

1. There is significant difference of Scheduled caste Parents' attitude towards girls' education in relation to Socio-Economic Status variation.
2. There is significant difference between the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents having high socio-economic status and having low socio-economic status towards girls' education in rural areas.
3. There is significant difference between the attitudes of Scheduled caste parents having high socio-economic status and having low socio-economic status towards girls' education in urban areas.

4.1. The Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

- The mass education and new consciousness will refine our personal beliefs and traditional system which are barriers to social progress. We should encourage the education of the women in all its ramifications in country. We need people both males and females who can lead to tumultuous ship to the safety. And probably, if we induce the training of our daughters, they could display their ingenuity to partake and calm the trouble sea.
- It is most fortunate nowadays that the gap and the spirit of social inequality in sexism is tremendously narrowed down. As at now throughout the globe education of learning which were deprived of them during the ninetieth century.
- Lloyd (2010) remarked that in modern sector of the economy men and women can occupy similar post in the adding or administrative work and the scarcity of educated women may result in a promotion rate more rapidly than that of their husbands.
- Although the study does not prevent to be conclusive in its evidence it is however necessary to bring to limelight factual observation which the researcher apprehended during his fieldwork.

4.2. Remedial Measures for further improvement of parental attitudes towards girls education

1. Parents with higher educational qualification have more understanding and awareness towards the education of girls than the parents with less educational qualification. It therefore, the educational facility should be provided the state administration in the said area from pre-primary to higher education as education has great value in the life and attitude of parents towards their girls children as the education is the means of change and transformation.

2. The parents with higher income have more awareness towards the education of girls as financial resources play great role in the education their girl children. No education can be provided properly without appropriate income. All works of life need money. Without money, nothing can be done.

3. Occupation like government employees and businessmen hold more awareness towards girl's education as the job of the parents is also playing a major role in the maintenance their family as well as their girl education.

4. Education, income and job of the parents play a great role in the education of girls' education. It is therefore, state administration will try to provide the opportunity to get educational facility, income generation programme from different funding agency, employment facility in the said community. So that, most of the parents will have the chance improve their educational level, income level as well as job opportunity in order to improve the quality and quantity of girls' education in the said community.

4.3. Implications for further research

The major limitations of the study on parental attitude towards education are that the quality of the estimates might have affected the reliability of the data. The errors arising out of lack of co-operation of the respondents, understanding of the language, exaggeration or evasion of information etc. might have affected the result. Social desirability factor might have played a role

in reporting of favourable attitude among parents. There may be wide differences between education levels of the different sub groups within the rural households because of multi religious population. This has not been taken care of. Mostly the respondents did not readily give the exact information without any assistance and this had caused a problem in the research work.

The present study opens up certain avenues for further research, which are:

- A similar study can be conducted by taking into consideration other variables such as parents' aspiration for their children, girls' academic performance etc.
- A comparative study can be undertaken among parents of different states and different countries.
- The influence of family background on girl-child education.
- The effect of parental attitude on the students' academic performance.
- The effect of early marriage and girl-child education.

4.4. Conclusion

The socio-economic factors concern the social and the economic steward of the people. The social economic factor is variable. It is subject to change depending on the moment of the society (either positive or negative) whether the people of West Bengal will have low or high socio-economic depends solely on the present administration. The prevailing economic sector or situation will determine whether the parents could afford to send their daughter to school or not. The prestigious factors are ascribable to the whim and caprices of the parents and the daughters alike. Both of them have lukewarm attitude for the acquisition of formal education. Some of the parents prefer their daughter becoming mother that to pursue education through few of them would want their daughter to achieve both motherhood and attainment of academic goals simultaneously. The daughters derive joy to have change their status in life from sprinter hood to motherhood than to relatively postpone that unique status to pursue academy. They are complacent because they are fulfilled the natural assignment. The discriminatory perspective

based on sex indicates the society is selective in employing labour into the workforce. Male are more regarded than female. Women employment is taken by some employees as supplementary to their marital and household management it is also evident that self-employment by women is profitable than civil services.

5.0. References

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